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D1.1 [Characterisation mechanisms for unknown data sources]

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Abstract

We describe a set of characterisation mechanisms focused on two data modalities: sensor-based and text-based stream data sources. By characterisation we refer to the process of semantically annotating data sources according to some domain or general ontologies, and/or linking these data sources to external publicly available knowledge sources (e.g. DBpedia). In the area of sensor data streams, we present work done for the ontology-based characterisation of environmental sensors from the SwissExperiment deployment in Switzerland, and for the characterisation of streaming data sources from the Pachube platform. We also describe the incipient work on the so-called Linked Stream Data or Linked Sensor Data, and present two alternative approaches to generate it. In the area of text stream characterisation, we describe techniques used for the characterisation of Web2.0 data sources, such as microblogs, by means of topic recognition and clustering.

[End of abstract]

Executive summary

This deliverable is focused on the characterisation of two main types of data sources (or modalities) that are currently available as streams: data from sensors (mainly environmental ones) and from social network platforms (mainly microblogs). By characterisation we refer to the process of semantically annotating data sources according to some domain or general ontologies, and/or linking these data sources to external publicly available knowledge sources (e.g. DBpedia). We have selected these two modalities for the work to be performed during this year as these were some of those proposed a priori in the PlanetData tasks, given their novelty and the cost of opportunity of applying characterisation techniques now.

The obtain results can be summarized as follow. If we start with sensor-based data, we can point to two different strands of work: one focused on the annotation of the data produced by sensors, and its publication in the Web of Linked Data, in what it is known as Linked Stream Data or Linked Sensor Data, and another one focused on the characterisation of the devices that produce data in an environmental domain, together with the observations that they produce, and the types of measurements that they generate. The latter exercise with several platforms(GSN and Pachube) shows that different platforms and deployments may need different techniques for the characterisation, and at the same time show that there are benefits that can be obtained from the application of such characterisation mechanisms, allowing a better search of relevant data streams.

In the context of Web2.0 data sources, mainly microblogs, we have shown that it is possible to characterise them by identifying relevant topics in them and by clustering them appropriately. This is just some initial characterisation work, and we will continue with it in the following period. Specifically it shows how different data sources may be aggregated, providing some hints about the potential integration of different modalities when characterising data sources.

To conclude, we have shown that it is possible to characterise these heterogeneous data sources to a good level of detail, and we have identified limitations of our approach, mainly due to the lack of information provided by users who own or publish these datasets, which makes this process more difficult to automate. As future work, we will mainly concentrate on the combination of data sources from different modalities, as proposed in the PlanetData work program.

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Abstract (for dissemination)	We describe a set of characterisation mechanisms focused on two data modalities: sensor-based and text-based stream data sources. In the area of sensor data streams, we present work done for the ontology-based characterisation of environmental sensors from the SwissExperiment deployment in Switzerland, and for the characterisation of streaming data sources from the Pachube platform. We also describe the incipient work on the so-called Linked Stream Data or Linked Sensor Data, and present two alternative approaches to generate it. In the area of text stream characterisation, we describe techniques used for the characterisation of Web2.0 data sources, such as microblogs, by means of topic recognition and clustering.
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Abbreviations

Nomenclature

API	Application Programming Interface
CQL	Continuous Query Language
DBMS	Database Management System
DSMS	Data Stream Management System
DUL	Dulce Ultra Light
GSN	Global Sensor Network
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
LSD	Linked Stream Data
O&M	Observation and Measurement
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OWL	Web Ontology Language
RBMS	Relational DataBase Management System
RDB2RDF	Relational Data Base To Resource Description Framework
RDF	Resource Description Framework
REST	Representational State Transfer
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
SMR	Sensor Metadata Repository
SSN XG	Semantic Sensor Network Working Group
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

1 Introduction

The objective of the work presented in this deliverable is to analyse several approaches that can be used in the characterization of dynamic data sources (normally available as data streams in a range of technological platforms) of different modalities. We have selected the following data modalities to focus on this work: numerical data streams from sensor networks and textual data streams from social networks. These data modalities and their characterisation have not been addressed yet thoroughly in the state of the art. We also analyse the obtained results in order to determine whether they could be applicable in the near future to those data modalities or to other additional ones.

It is important to note that it is not an objective of our work to be exhaustive in the description and use of all the possible characterisation approaches that could be applied to the selected data modalities, and more specifically to the selected data sources used for experimentation. Neither is our objective to be exhaustive in the range of data modalities that could be characterised for dynamic data sets (for instance, we do not address multimedia content or graph-based information, which are also common data modalities available nowadays).

It is also important to note that this deliverable focuses on the characterisation of single-modality data sources. During the next period in PlanetData we will focus on the characterisation of multi-modality data sources, and on the integration and fusion of data across modalities, always considering dynamic data sources available as a form of data streams. This will be reported in deliverable D1.4, in month 24.

Finally, given our semantic and Web-based approach for the characterisation and management of data sources in PlanetData, we will pay special attention to how data streams can be supported and published in a Web context, in the form of Linked Data. This is known as Linked Stream Data (or more specifically when data is coming from sensors, Linked Sensor Data).

1.1 Background: Data streams and modalities

Traditional data management systems, such as Relational Database Management Systems (RDBMS), normally have focused on handling rather static data, in the sense that updates to databases are done at a frequency that in general allows access to all stored data almost at anytime and allows answering queries based on those data. While their scalability even for high frequency updates and large data sizes has been proven and improved over the years, new types of challenges have arisen during the last years, especially related to the higher dynamicity of the data sources that they have to handle (which leads into the creation of the term "stream data"). Compared to static data, stream data has several unique characteristics, such as being continuous and ordered, and it can normally be read only once. To handle these data streams, new database-oriented techniques and systems, such as Data Stream Management Systems [55], have been developed, and other techniques and their associated technology, such as Complex-Event Processing [51], have been also developed.

An analysis of the behaviour of this type of systems is one of the foci of PlanetData deliverable 1.4.

Physical sensors are, for instance, an important source of such type of data, since they produce data taken from their observation of some phenomena in a continuous manner, and at rates that are determined by the application needs or by the hardware limitations. Examples of such sensors are humidity and temperature sensors deployed in forests or beaches, energy-consumption sensors deployed in houses, light sensors deployed in city lamps, etc. There are also other types of sensors that are called virtual sensors, and which can be the result of some computation or integration over the data produced by physical sensors, or be related to human activity such as the production of continuous news/blogs/tweets produced by certain organizations or people.

These data streams, of different modalities, are used in a large number of domains, such as telecommunication, stock market, networking, traffic control, environmental monitoring, etc. In the telecommunication industry, for instance, streams of calling number records made by users can be analyzed to detect fraud. In the stock market, the streams of transactions can be used to monitor the stock value behaviour of a certain company. In the networking industry, streams of data can be monitored to detect the existence of e-mail worms. In traffic control, streams of records detecting vehicles passing through a certain street can be used to predict the possible congestion and warn other drivers to reroute. In environmental monitoring, streams of sensor data can be used to detect whether a certain area has high risk of experiencing fire or flood. These are only some examples of how this type of data can be used.

1.2 Objectives

Given this range of applications, the possibility of characterising an incoming data stream that is unknown a priori or for which not much information is available may be useful in determining whether it can be used for a specific application, or whether it fulfills a set of information needs. This can be done by using stream mining techniques. However, the research on the characterisation of data streams by means of data-stream learning and stream summarization techniques is still in an early stage [27], and more work has to be done in order to be able to characterize these types of sources when they are unknown a priori. Good descriptions of the state of the art in this area and of open challenges can be found at: [26], [28], [29]. This is also, for instance, the core of the work that is presented and discussed in international conferences and workshops like SensorKDD ¹. As we will see throughout this deliverable, the characterising an incoming data streams will enable us to consult external knowledge sources in order to retrieve more information that is coming from sensor data (as in the case of our work in Pachube2RDF), consulting metadata registry in order to have an integrated view of sensor metadata information (as in our work of GSN with metadata repository), or analyzing streams of text (as in our work in

¹<http://www.ornl.gov/sci/knowledgediscovery/SensorKDD-2011/>

characterising and clustering Twitter streams).

In the specific area of sensor network characterization, two aspects may be considered. The first one is the characterisation of the data streams that is produced by sensors, where the application of some of the aforementioned techniques is possible, in order to characterise the numerical distribution of data, for instance. The second one is the provision of metadata about the sensor platforms, which also allows describing at a semantic level the type of data and observations that are obtained from that hardware infrastructure. In this context, until recently there has not been a standardized model to describe sensor networks in a way that can ease the discovery of new sensor network based data sources in existing registries (e.g., Sensorbase, Pachube), or to facilitate the task of optimizing data fusion and integration techniques. Now the work done by the W3C SSN incubator group has resulted in the publication of a Sensor Network Ontology that can be used for this characterisation.

Similarly, different techniques may be used for the characterisation of text streams, as we will see in this deliverable, ranging from clustering techniques to topic identification, among others.

1.3 Document organisation

The organization of this document is as follows. Chapter 2 discusses characterisation mechanisms for Sensor Data Streams, that have been done in the context of PlanetData, focusing on sensor data available in two different and widespread platforms, such as GSN and Pachube. We describe especially how we exploit the Semantic Sensor Network Ontology developed in the context of the W3C Semantic Sensor Network Incubator Group(SSN-XG), where PlanetData members have participated actively, for the description of the sensor devices and of the observations and data that can be generated from them in these platforms, with the aim of improving the registries of both platforms. Chapter 3 surveys existing work regarding properties of Linked Stream Data in detail, and more focus is given on the activity guideline of how to publish and consume it. Chapter 4 describes our work in the context of PlanetData that has been done regarding characterisation mechanisms for text streams. Chapter 5 presents the conclusion of this document.

2 Characterisation mechanisms for Sensor Data Streams

In this section we will summarize two efforts that we have done for the characterisation of sensor-based data streams, and more specifically for the ontology-based description of sensor networks that produce sensor data, so that these data sources can be discovered more easily. These efforts are focused on providing such descriptive metadata to the Global Sensor Network (GSN) platform [2] and to the Pachube platform ². In the first case it is not only focused on providing this descriptive metadata, but also ensuring, once that the metadata is generated and the sensor data streams are characterised according to existing ontologies, access through an extension of SPARQL for data streams. In the case of Pachube, we have only focused on the provision of metadata.

Before starting with the description of these characterisation approaches, we will describe briefly the Semantic Sensor Network Ontology that has been developed in the context of the W3C Semantic Sensor Network incubator group, since this ontology is an essential part in both efforts, as it describes the general model to be used for the description of sensors and sensor networks.

2.1 The W3C Semantic Sensor Network Ontology

Earlier work has been done to represent sensors and their associated observations in the context of the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) Observation and Measurements (O&M) model. This model is represented as an XML schema, and the specification of the model is available as an OGC document. O&M main components are feature of interest, sensors, and properties. Sensors are the entities that emit stream data. Features are the entities to be measured and properties are observable characteristics. For example, a heart rate sensor that is deployed on Bob's heart, has heart rate as the property and Bob as the feature.

More recent work has been done by the W3C Semantic Sensor Network (SSN) Incubator Group in the design of a SSN Ontology ³ that can be the basis for the description of sensor networks and sensors, and that can be used, as we will describe later in this deliverable, for the generation of Linked Sensor Data. Figure 1 depicts an overview of the SSN ontology.

The main classes of the Semantic Sensor Network ontology have been aligned with classes in the DOLCE Ultra Lite (DUL) foundational ontology to facilitate reuse and interoperability.

A full description of this ontology is available in the SSN-XG final report pointed out above.

The SSN ontology (See Figure 2) can be viewed and used for capturing various properties of entities in the real world. For instance it can be used to describe sensors, how they function and process the external stimuli. Alternatively it

²<http://www.pachube.com/>

³http://www.w3.org/2005/Incubator/ssn/wiki/Report_Work_on_the_SSN_ontology

Figure 1: Overview of the W3C SSN Ontology

can be centered on the observed data, and its associated metadata [38]. In this study, we employ the latter ontology modeling approach in a large-scale real sensor network application, the Swiss Experiment. For instance consider a wind-monitor sensor in a weather station deployed at a field site. The sensor is capable of measuring the wind speed on its specific location. Suppose that another sensor attached at the same station reports air temperature every 10 minutes. In terms of the SSN ontology both the wind and temperature measurements can be seen as observations, each of them with a different feature of interest (wind and air), and each referring to a different property (speed and temperature).

In the SSN ontology, instances of the **Observation** class represent such observations, e.g. Listing 1, and are linked to a certain feature instance through a **featureOfInterest** property. Similarly the **observedProperty** links to an instance of a property, such as speed. Since the SSN model is intended to be generic, it does not define the possible types of observed properties, but these can be taken from a specialized vocabulary such as the NASA SWEET⁴ ontology. Actual values of the sensor output can also be represented as instances linked to the **SensorOutput** class through the **hasValue** property. The data itself can

⁴<http://sweet.jpl.nasa.gov/> NASA SWEET Ontology

Figure 2: Main concepts of the SSN ontology.

```

swissex:WindSpeedObservation1 rdf:type ssn:Observation;
  ssn:featureOfInterest [ rdf:type sweet:Wind];
  ssn:observedProperty [ rdf:type sweetProp:Speed].
  ssn:observationResult
    [ rdf:type ssn:SensorOutput;
      ssn:hasValue [qudt:numericValue "6.245"^^xsd:double]];
  ssn:observedBy swissex:SensorWind1;

```

Listing 1: Wind Speed observation in RDF according to the SSN ontology

be linked through a specialized property of a quantity ontology (e.g. the QUDT⁵ `numericValue` property). Finally the observation can be linked to a particular sensor (e.g. Sensor instance `SensorWind1` through the `observedBy` property). Evidently more information about the observation can be recored, including units, accuracy, noise, failures, etc. Notice that the process of ontology modeling requires reuse and combination of the SSN ontology and domain-specific ontologies.

2.2 Characterisation and access mechanisms for the GSN platform

This growing use of sensors also increases the difficulty for applications to manage and query sensor data [22]. This difficulty becomes even more noticeable when applications need to search for a particular information set over federated and heterogeneous sensor networks, providing huge volumes of sensor data to large user communities [39]. In these environments, sensors from different vendors and with specific characteristics are installed and added to a system. Each of them produces different values, with different data schemas, precision or ac-

⁵Quantities, Units, Dimensions and Data Types ontologies, <http://www.qudt.org/>

curacy, and in different units of measurement. This heterogeneity complicates the task of querying sensor data as well as the corresponding metadata.

A rich body of research work has addressed the problem of querying data in large-scale sensor networks [56, 3, 49, 72]. These studies generally focused on indexing sensor data, caching query results, and maximizing the shares of data to be carried together over networks. Whilst these methods substantially improve the query processing performance, they do not sufficiently consider the importance and difficulty of heterogeneous (sensor) data integration. In contrast, studies on semantic-aware sensor data management [21, 7, 14, 71, 35] have introduced a wide variety of mechanisms that search and reason over semantically enriched sensor data, while considering the heterogeneous characteristics of sensing environments. However, these proposals are still insufficient to show how to manage sensor data and metadata in a federated sensor network, and to efficiently process queries in a distributed environment.

In this section, we describe a framework that enables efficient ontology-based querying of sensor data in a federated sensor network, going beyond state-of-the-art storage and querying technologies. The key features of the framework are briefly highlighted as follows:

- Our framework supports semantic-enriched query processing based on ontology information—for example, two users may name two sensors as of types “temperature” and “thermometer”, yet the query processing in the framework can recognize that both sensors belong to the same type and include them in query results.
- The framework employs the SSN ontology⁶, along with domain-specific ontologies, for effectively modeling the underlying heterogeneous sensor data sources, and establishes mappings between the current sensor data model and the SSN ontology observations using a declarative mapping language.
- The framework enables scalable search over distributed sensor data. Specifically, the query processor first looks up ontology-enabled metadata to effectively find which distributed nodes maintain the sensor data satisfying a given query condition. It then dynamically composes URL API requests to the corresponding data sources at the distributed GSN⁷ nodes.
- Our framework has been developed in close collaboration with expert users from environmental science and engineering, and thus reflects central and immediate requirements on the use of federated sensor networks of the affected user community. The resulting system has been running as the backbone of the Swiss Experiment platform⁸, a large-scale real federated sensor network.

⁶W3C Semantic Sensor Network (SSN-XG) Ontology [45]

⁷Global Sensor Networks [1], streaming data middleware used for the prototype.

⁸Swiss-Experiment: <http://www.swiss-experiment.ch/>

```

swissex:SensorWind1 rdf:type ssn:Sensor;
  ssn:onPlatform [:hasGeometry [rdf:type wgs84:Point;
                                wgs84:lat "46.8037166";
                                wgs84:long "9.7780305"]];
  ssn:observes [rdf:type sweetProp:WindSpeed] .

```

Listing 2: Representation of a Sensor on a platform and its location in RDF

```

wan7: {wind_speed_scalar_av FLOAT, timed DATETIME}
imis_wbfe: {vw FLOAT, timed DATETIME}

```

Listing 3: Heterogeneous sensor schemas

2.2.1 Modeling Sensor Data with Ontologies

In our study, we use the SSN ontology to describe The Swiss Experiment sensor network deployment, by means of adding metadata to it. For example we can specify that the weather station platform where both sensors are installed, is geo-spatially located, using the SG84 vocabulary⁹. In the example in Listing 2, the location (latitude and longitude) of the platform of the `SensorWind1` sensor is provided. We can also include other information such as a responsible person, initial date of the deployment, etc.

Although the observation model provides a semantically enriched representation of the data, sensors generally produce streams of raw data with very little structure and thus there is a gap between the observation model and the original data. For instance both sensors in Listing 3 (`wan7` and `imis_wbfe`) capture wind speed measurements but have different schemas, each one stores the observed value in a different attribute. To query wind speed observations in these settings, the user needs to know the names of the sensors, and the names of all different attributes that match with the semantic concept of wind speed. This is an error-prone task and is unfeasible when the number of sensors is large.

We take an ontology mapping-based approach to overcome this problem. Although in previous works [59, 8] sensor observations are provided and published as RDF and linked data, they do not provide the means and representation that allows querying live sensor data in terms of an ontological model. Going beyond these approaches, we propose using declarative mappings that express how to construct SSN Observations from raw sensor schemas, and for this purpose we use the W3C RDB2RDF Group, R2RML language¹⁰ to represent the mappings. For example we can specify that for every tuple of the `wan7` sensor, an instance of a SSN `ObservationValue` must be created, using the mapping definition `Wan7WindMap` depicted in Fig. 3 (See Listing 4 for its R2RML representation).

The instance URI is composed according to the mapping `rr:template` rule

⁹ Basic Geo WGS84 Vocabulary: <http://www.w3.org/2003/01/geo/>

¹⁰ R2RML mapping language, <http://www.w3.org/2001/sw/rdb2rdf/r2rml/>

Figure 3: Simple mapping from the wan7 sensor to a SSN ObservationValue

```

:Wan7WindMap a rr:TriplesMapClass;
  rr:tableName "wan7";
  rr:subjectMap
    [ rr:template
      "http://swissex.ch/data#Wan5/WindSpeed/ObsValue{timed}";
      rr:column "timed";
      rr:class ssn:ObservationValue;
      rr:graph swissex:WannengratWindSpeed.srdf ];
  rr:predicateObjectMap
    [ rr:predicateMap [ rr:predicate qudt:numericValue ];
      rr:objectMap [ rr:column "wind_speed_scalar_av" ] ]; .
  
```

Listing 4: Mapping a sensor to a SSN ObservationValue in R2RML

that concatenates the `timed` column value to a prefix. The observation actual value is extracted from the `wind_speed_scalar_av` sensor field and is linked to the `ObservationValue` through a `qudt:numericValue` property.

By using the mappings and the SSN ontology, we are able to express the sensor metadata and observations data using a semantic model, even if the underlying data sources are relational streams. In the next section we provide details about the query translation process that is carried out to make querying possible.

2.2.2 Querying Ontology-based Sensor Data

Ontology-based streaming data access aims at generating semantic web content from existing streaming data sources [17]. Although previous efforts have been made in order to provide semantic content automatically from relational databases using mappings [63], only recently this idea has been explored in the context of data stream management [17]. Our approach in this deliverable

(Fig. 4) covers this gap, extending the work of [17] to support the R2RML syntax and produce algebra expressions that can be transformed into requests to federated sensor networks.

Figure 4: Ontology-based sensor query service: translation of $\text{SPARQL}_{\text{Stream}}$ queries over virtual RDF streams, to requests over federated sensor networks

Our ontology-based sensor query service receives queries specified in terms of the SSN ontology using $\text{SPARQL}_{\text{Stream}}$ [17], an extension of SPARQL that supports operators over RDF streams such as time windows, and has been inspired by C-SPARQL [7]. Since the $\text{SPARQL}_{\text{Stream}}$ query is expressed in terms of the ontology, it has to be transformed into queries in terms of the data sources, using a set of mappings, expressed in R2RML. The language is used to define declarative mappings from relational sources to datasets in RDF, as detailed in Section 2.2.1. These are in fact *virtual RDF streams*, since they are not materialized beforehand, but the data is queried and transformed on demand after the $\text{SPARQL}_{\text{Stream}}$ query is translated. The target of this *query translation* process is a streaming query expression over the sensor streams. These queries are represented as algebra expressions extended with time window constructs, so that optimizations can be performed over them and can be easily translated to a target language or stream request, such as an API URL, as we will see in Section 2.2.3.

As an example, consider the mapping in Fig. 5, which extends the one displayed before in Fig. 3. This mapping generates not only the `ObservationValue` instance but also a `SensorOutput` and an `Observation` for each record of the sensor `wan7`. Notice that each of these instances constructs its URI with a different template rule and the `Observation` has a `observedProperty` property to the `WindSpeed` property defined in the SWEET ontology.

The following query (Listing 5), obtains all wind-speed observation values greater than some threshold (e.g. 10) in the last 5 hours, from the sensors

Figure 5: Mapping from the wan7 sensor to an Observation and its properties

virtual RDF stream `swissex:WannengratWindSensors.srdf`. Such queries are issued by geo-scientists to collect filtered observations and feed their prediction models.

Using the mapping definitions, the query translator can compose the corresponding algebra expression that creates a time window of 5 hours over the wan7 sensor, applies a selection with the predicate `wind_speed_scalar_av > 10`, and finally projects the `wind_speed_scalar_av` and `timed` columns (See Fig. 6).

Figure 6: Translation of the query in Listing 5 to an algebra expression, using the R2RML mappings.

The algebra expressions can be transformed to continuous queries in languages such as CQL [4] or SNEEQl [13], and then executed by a streaming query engine. In the case of GSN as the query engine, the algebra expression can be used to produce a sensor data request to the stream query engine. Specifically,

```

PREFIX ssn: <http://purl.oclc.org/NET/ssnx/ssn#>
PREFIX swissex: <http://swiss-experiment.ch/metadata#>
PREFIX qudt: <http://data.nasa.gov/qudt/owl/qudt#>
PREFIX sweetSpeed: <http://sweet.jpl.nasa.gov/2.1/propSpeed.owl#>
SELECT ?speed ?obs
FROM NAMED STREAM swissex:WannengratWindSpeed.srdf [NOW - 5 HOUR ]
WHERE {
  ?obs      a ssn:Observation;
            ssn:observationResult ?result;
            ssn:observedProperty ?prop.
  ?prop     a sweetSpeed:WindSpeed.
  ?result   ssn:hasValue ?obsvalue.
  ?obsvalue a ssn:ObservationValue;
            qudt:numericValue ?speed.
  FILTER ( ?speed > 10 ) }

```

Listing 5: SPARQLStream query

the query engine in our framework processes the requests and returns a result set that matches the SPARQLStream criteria. To complete the query processing, the result set is transformed by the *data translation* process to ontology instances (SPARQL bound variables or RDF, depending if it is a SELECT or a CONSTRUCT query).

Figure 7: Algebra UNION expression, with two additional wind-speed sensors.

Depending on the mappings available, the resulting algebra expression can become entirely different. For instance, suppose that there are similar mappings for the `windsensor1` and `windsensor2` sensors, also measuring wind-speed values as `wan7`. Then the resulting expression would be similar to the one in Fig. 7, but including all three sensors in a UNION expression. Conversely, a mapping for a sensor that observes a property different than `sweetSpeed:WindSpeed` will be ignored in the translation process for the sample query.

2.2.3 System Overview

Using the ontology-based approach for streaming data described in the previous section, we have built a sensor data search prototype implementation for the Swiss-Experiment project. The system (Fig. 8) consists of the following main components: the user interface, the federated GSN stream server instances, the sensor metadata repository and the ontology-based sensor query processor.

Figure 8: System architecture

- **User Interface.** The web-based user interface is designed to help the user filtering criteria to narrow the number of sensors to be queried (Fig. 9). Filtering criteria may include the sensing capabilities of the devices, e.g. select only the sensors that measure air temperature or wind speed. It is also possible to filter according to the characteristics of the deployment or platform, e.g. select sensors deployed in a particular region, delimited by a geo-referenced bounding box. It is also possible to filter by both data and metadata parameters. For instance the user may filter only those sensors registering air temperature values higher than 30 degrees. The filtering parameters can be passed to the ontology-based query processor, as a `SPARQLStream` query in terms of the SSN ontology as detailed next.
- **Ontology-based Sensor Query Processor.** This component is capable of processing the `SPARQLStream` queries received from the user interface, and perform the query processing over the metadata repository and the GSN stream data engine. The ontology-based processor uses the previously defined R2RML mappings and the sensor metadata in the RDF repository to generate the corresponding requests for GSN.

The ontology-based query service delegates the processing to the GSN server instances by composing *data requests* according to the GSN web-service or URL interfaces. In the case of the web service, a special GSN wrapper for the WSDL specification¹¹ has been developed, that can be

¹¹GSN Web Service Interface: <http://gsn.svn.sourceforge.net/viewvc/gsn/branches/documentations/misc/gsn-webservice-api.pdf>

Figure 9: Sensor data search user interface

```

http://montblanc.slf.ch:22001/multidata?vs[0]=wan7&
field[0]=wind_speed_scalar_av&
from=15/05/2011+05:00:00&to=15/05/2011+10:00:00&
c_vs[0]=wan7s&c_field[0]=wind_speed_scalar_av&c_min[0]=10

```

Listing 6: Generation of a GSN API URL

used if the user requires to obtain the observations as RDF instances, just as described in Section 2.2.2. Alternatively, the ontology-based sensor query processor can generate GSN API¹² URLs from the algebra expressions. These URLs link directly to the GSN server that provides the data with options such as bulk download, CSV formatting, etc.

For example, the expression in Fig. 6 produces the GSN API URL in Listing 6. The first part is the GSN host (<http://montblanc.slf.ch:22001>). Then the sensor name and fields are specified with the `vs` and `field` parameters. The `from-to` part represents the time window and finally the last line specifies the selection of values greater than 10 (with the `c_min` parameter). These URLs are presented in each sensor info-box in the user interface map.

With this semantically enabled sensor data infrastructure, users can issue complex queries that exploit the existing relationships of the metadata

¹²GSN Web URL API: <http://sourceforge.net/apps/trac/gsn/wiki/web-interfacev1-server>

```

PREFIX ssn: <http://purl.oclc.org/NET/ssnx/ssn#>
PREFIX omgeo: <http://www.ontotext.com/owlim/geo#>
PREFIX dul: <http://www.loa-cnr.it/ontologies/DUL.owl#>
PREFIX swissex: <http://swiss-experiment.ch/metadata#>
PREFIX sweet: <http://sweet.jpl.nasa.gov/2.1/prop.owl#>
SELECT ?obs ?sensor
FROM NAMED STREAM swissex:WannengratSensors.srdf [NOW - 5 HOUR ]
WHERE {
  ?obs      a ssn:Observation;
           ssn:observedBy ?sensor.
  ?sensor   ssn:observes ?prop;
           ssn:onPlatform ?platform.
  ?platform dul:hasLocation [swissex:hasGeometry ?geo].
  ?geo      omgeo:within(46.85 9.75 47.31 10.08) .
  ?prop     a sweet:MotionProperty.
}

```

Listing 7: SPARQL_{Stream} query for the ontology-based sensor metadata search

and also the mappings, such as the one in (Listing 7).

This query requests the observations and originating sensor in the last 5 hours, for the region specified by a bounding box, and only for those sensors that measure motion properties. The geo-location query boundaries are specified using the `omgeo:within` function, and RDF semantic stores such as OWLIM¹³ use semantic spatial indexes to compute these kind of queries. Regarding the observed property, considering that the `MotionProperty` is defined in the SWEET ontology as a superclass of all motion-related properties such as Wind Speed, Acceleration or Velocity, all sensors that capture these properties are considered in the query.

In all these examples, the users do not need to know the particular names of the real sensors, nor they need to know all the sensor attribute names that represent an observable property. This clearly eases the task for research scientists, who can easily use and access the data they need, with little knowledge of the technical details of the heterogeneous sensor schemas and their definitions. Also, this framework enables easily plugging new sensors to the system, without changing any existing query and without programming. All previous queries would seamlessly include new sensors, if their metadata and mappings are present in the repository.

- **GSN Server Instances.** Our ontology-based approach for sensor querying relies on the existence of efficient stream query engines that support live sensor querying and that can be deployed in a federated environment. In the Swiss-Experiment project, the sensor data is maintained with Global Sensor Networks (GSN)[1], a processor that supports flexible integration of sensor networks and sensor data, provides distributed querying and filtering, as well as dynamic adaptation and configuration.

The Swiss-Experiment project has several GSN instances deployed in different locations which operate independently. In this way they can effi-

¹³OWLIM: <http://www.ontotext.com/owlim>

ciently perform their query operations locally, and can be accessed using the interfaces mentioned earlier. However the metadata for these instances is centralized in the RDF metadata repository, enabling the federation of these GSN instances as described in the previous subsection.

- **Sensor Metadata Repository.** We have used the Sesame¹⁴ RDF store for managing the centralized sensor metadata, using the SSN ontology. The entire set of sensor metadata is managed with the Sensor Metadata Repository (SMR)[39]. The SMR is a web-based collaborative environment based on Semantic Wiki technologies [70], which includes not only static metadata but also dynamic metadata including the information of outliers and anomalies or remarks on particular value sets. This system provides an easy and intuitive way of submitting and editing their metadata without any programming.

In SMR each sensor, platform or deployment has an associated Wiki page where the data can be semantically annotated with attribute-value pairs, and entities can be connected to each other with semantic properties. This allows interlinking related pages and also dynamically generating rich content for the users, based on the annotated metadata. The entire contents of the SMR can be queried programmatically using the SPARQL language, making it usable not only for humans but also for machines.

2.2.4 Experimental Evaluation

In order to validate our approach we have conducted a series of experiments in the sensor data and metadata system described previously. The goals were to (i) analyze empirically the scalability of semantic sensor metadata queries and (ii) assess the query and data transformation overhead of our approach. For the first objective, we compared a straightforward (but currently used by scientists) way of obtaining all sensors that measure a particular property (e.g. temperature), with our approach. The former consists in getting sensor details from every sensor in every deployment in the distributed system, and then comparing the sensor attribute name with the property name.

In our environment we have 28 deployments (aprox. 50 sensors in each one), running on its own GSN instance accessible through a web service interface. Therefore to perform this operation the client must contact all of these services to get the required information, making it very inefficient as the number of deployments increases (See Fig. 10). Conversely, using our centralized semantic search we eliminated the need of contacting the GSN instances at all for this type of query, as it can be solved by exploring the sensor metadata, looking for those sensors that have a `ssn:observes` relationship with the desired property.

As we see in Fig. 10 it is not only scalable as we add more deployments, but we also provide an answer that is independent of the syntactic name assigned to the sensor attributes.

¹⁴Sesame: <http://www.openrdf.org/>

Figure 10: Comparing metadata search: obtain all sensors that measure temperature. The naïve vs. semantic centralized approach.

Our approach sometimes incurs in a computing overhead when translating the `SPARQLStream` queries to the internal algebra and the target language or URL request, using the mapping definitions. We analyzed this by comparing the query times of a raw GSN service request and a `SPARQLStream` query translated to an equivalent GSN request. We executed this test over a single simulated deployment, first with only one sensor and up to 9 sensors with data updates every 500 ms. The query continuously obtains observations from the sensors in the last 10 minutes, filtering values smaller than a fixed constant, similarly to Listing 5.

As we show in Fig. 11 the overhead is of roughly 1.5 seconds for the test case. Notice that the overhead is seemingly constant as we add more sensors to the mappings. However this is a continuous query and the translation time penalty has been excluded from the computation, as this operation is only executed once, then the query can be periodically executed. In any case this additional overhead is also displayed in Fig. 11 and it degrades as the number of mappings to sensors increases. This is likely because mappings are stored and loaded as files, and not cached in any way. More efficient management of large collections of mappings could throw better results for the translation operation. Nevertheless we show that continuous queries have an acceptable overhead, almost constant for the chosen use-case.

Figure 11: Query execution and translation overhead: comparing a raw query vs. query translation.

2.3 Characterisation mechanisms for the Pachube platform

Pachube¹⁵ is a platform that enables users to publish the measurement of different type of sensors on the web, and retrieving those measurements using a REST API or through a map-based user interface. It offers support for remote environments interactions, as well as structured metadata describing the sensor data streams. Thus, Pachube can be considered as a part of the Sensor Web or Sensor Internet. In order to do this, Pachube designed a very useful yet simple data structure, with three main components, which are Environment, Datastream, and Datapoint. An Environment represents the place where there are things to be measured by sensors. Examples of Environment are a building, a forest. A Datastream represents sensor that is deployed within an environment and a Datapoint represents a single value emitted on the datastream on a specific stream. Users are able to attach free tags, for example attaching *Celsius* or *Outside Temperature*. Hence it does not follow the OGC Observations and Measurements model.

Publishers can send their data from a sensor node for storage, making it available to other users. Each sensor node has a unique id and can send more data streams from different sensor devices. When registering a sensor node on Pachube the publisher can also provide a description of the data sensed

¹⁵<http://www.pachube.com>

Domain	Tag	Number of occurrences
Temperature related tags	temperature	336
	Temperature	42
	temp	32
	celsius	293
Power consumption related tags	electricity	389
	power	34
	watts	34
No description	null	1437
	Distinct tags	Data streams
Total	2238	9466

Figure 12: Frequent tags for data streams descriptions in Pachube

which can include information about the location of the sensor (latitude and longitude), exposure of the sensor node (indoor or outdoor), tags and units of measurements for a data stream. The descriptions are in XML format and besides the publisher data they also contain automatically generated data, such as timestamp of the last update, the current status of the sensor node (live or frozen) or minimum and maximum values for a specific stream.

A particular aspect of these descriptions is the tags used for describing a data stream. These tags are introduced by the sensor publisher and they play a major role in sensor discovery, as one would use the tags when searching for a specific type of sensors. We have analyzed over 3700 sensor description which provide over 9400 data streams. The most frequent tags that are available by the time of writing this document are presented in Figure 12. It can be observed that for a single domain, like temperature monitoring, there can be several different tags that describe the data streams. This can bring difficulties in sensor discovery since a simple search by tag will not reveal all the sensors that one may be interested in.

While Pachube may bring the benefits of the Sensor Web, the lack of semantics in the values that are produced, and in the descriptions of the sensors and the types of features and observations that they produce makes it difficult for users to exploit the full potential of it. For example, with the current design of Pachube, there is no way to search for all sensors measuring temperature. Furthermore, there are no links to other useful datasets or URIs which would enable retrieving more useful information about the location where a sensor is, or about the sensor itself, as we described previously. For example, the Datastream might indicate measurement of *Celsius*, but there is no further information about this concept. While a human might process this information with her background knowledge to link this information with temperature, a machine/computer will have no idea at all what to do with the tag *Celsius*.

In this section, we describe our proposal for aligning the sensor output emitted by Pachube with the W3C SSN ontology concepts. Besides, we propose linking these sensors descriptions to DBpedia¹⁶ terms. More methodological details about the steps to be followed for this process will be provided in the following section, so here we mainly concentrate on the challenges to be overcome with Pachube.

2.3.1 Modelling

One of the tasks to be performed is that of modeling, which requires activities for modelling the database, the ontology and the mappings between both.

1. Database design of Pachube Sensor Output. There is no documentation regarding the schema of Pachube Sensor Output. So, we perform this task by analyzing the JSON output of Pachube together with its API and we selected some of the most important concepts to be the tables of our database. Those concepts are Environment, Datastream, Datapoint, Location, and Tag. In addition to them, we also add some concepts of SSN to be tables, such as Feature Of Interest and Property. The database design of Pachube2RDF can be seen on Figure 13.
2. Ontology Modeling. We use the SSN Ontology as a basis for our work here. More specifically, we have chosen the data perspective, which focuses on the data and observation values. Some of the SSN classes we are focusing are System, Platform, Deployment, Sensor, SensorOutput, ObservationValue, and Property.
3. Mapping Modeling. This sub-task defines the mappings between Pachube database tables with SSN classes. The mappings are defined as the following
 - Table Environment is mapped to class *System*, *Platform* and *Deployment*.
 - Table Datastream is mapped to class *Sensor*.
 - Table Datapoint is mapped to class *SensorOutput* and *ObservationValue*.
 - Table Tag is mapped to class *Tag*.

The mapping is specified with D2R Mapping Language [11].

Once these models are generated, we proceed to the generation of instances of the SSN ontology from the Pachube Sensor Output. Instances of some classes mapped with D2R Mapping Language are automatically created by D2R Engine [11]. However, some other instances have to be created without D2R Server, such as *Property* and *FeatureOfInterest*. Class *Property* defines an observable

¹⁶<http://www.dbpedia.org>

Figure 13: Pachube2RDF Database Diagram

quality of an Object, such as temperature, humidity, and so on. Class *Feature-OfInterest* defines the entity whose quality was observed. Example of Feature of Interest are air, room, and so on. Because Pachube tags are defined in free-form, in which users can enter any values on it, there is additional work to be done in order to generate instances of *Property* and *FeatureOfInterest*.

2.3.2 Generating semantics from user-generated tags

The tags used to describe data streams are important in determining the type of measurements that a sensor emits (e.g temperature, light intensity, power consumption). Nevertheless, other important features of a sensor can be found in its XML description. For instance, the geographical location of the sensor, if it is in an indoor or outdoor environment, or if it sends data from a physical or virtual environment, are important features that should be taken into consideration when interested in using these data streams.

In order to process the Pachube Sensor Output, we propose to consult external knowledge sources. We will show how we process Pachube tags that relate Feature of Interest and Unit of Measure with DBpedia, and Location using Cyc [46].

We propose a mechanism of generating instances of *Property* class using the following procedures:

1. Tag Normalization. The first step to process a tag is to normalize it. Tags can be in a single or compound words, and vary between full words or abbreviations. The first step is to start each tag upper case. Thus, the tag *temperature* is converted into *Temperature*. Tags that are abbreviations are expanded, for example tag *temp* and *C* have to be transformed into *Temperature* and *Celsius* respectively. Tags in the form of compound words are splitted, and each of the splitted words has to be expanded in case it is an abbreviation and only the first word has to be capitalized. All spaces in the compound word tag are converted into underline characters. For example, tag *Outside Temp* will be converted into *Outside_temperature*.
2. Top K Tags Calculation. After the tag is normalized, a calculation is made to determine whether the tag is in the top k tags or no. This calculation is important because there are unlimited variants of tags and we only process some of the popular tags. The calculation of this task uses a modified version of Space Saving Algorithm [53]. The Space Saving Algorithm maintains partial information of items, and only monitors a subset of the elements.

Listing 8: Original Space Saving Algorithm

```

def CalculateTags(tag) :
  for each element tag in the stream
    if tag is monitored: Increment counttag
    else
      Let tagmin be the element with least hits min
      Replace tagmin with tag with counttag = min + 1

```

As we can see on Listing 8, the original algorithm works in a non deterministic way in case there are several elements/tags with the same count *min* and the minimum count tag is always removed by a new tag, even though the tag has occurred for a long time. This is possible because value count attached to a tag is not its absolute value of number of times the tag appear, because a new tag can appear in the top k tag with the count value attached as the value of the previous minimal tag plus one. Thus, we propose to include absolute value of the number occurrences of the tag, and using tag weight when determining which tag to be removed. The tag weight can be calculated as the combination between the absolute and relative count values. The Space Saving Algorithm in Pachube2RDF can be seen on Listing 9.

Listing 9: Modified Space Saving Algorithm

```

def CalculateTags(tag) :
  for each element tag in the stream
    if tag is monitored
      Increment  $count_{tag}$ 
      Increment  $absolute_{tag}$ 
    else
      Let ratio represent the importance level of relative count
       $0 < ratio < 1$ 
      Let  $tag_{min}$  be the element with least weight
       $weight = (ratio * count) + ((1 - ratio) * absolute)$ 
      Replace  $tag_{min}$  with tag with
       $count_{tag} = count_{tag_{min}} + 1$ 
       $absolute_{tag} = 1$ 

```

Listing 10: Query of Tag Using SKOS Subject

```

select distinct ?o where {
  <http://dbpedia.org/resource/Temperature>
  <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#subject>
  ?o
}

```

3. Alignment With External Knowledge. After retrieving the top K tags, we categorize those tags into four categories: property(temperature, humidity, etc), unit of measure(celsius, watt, etc), feature of interest(room,air,etc), and miscellaneous(success, failure, not used, c2b553762f68, C6979, R1 Bottom, and so on). We consult DBpedia by querying for SKOS subject property attached to the DBpedia resource corresponding to the tag. For example, the tag *Temperature* will generate a query in the listing 10.

If Cyc is preferred, then OpenCyc tagger can be used, and there are two ways to consult it, either using web service or Java API. This URL¹⁷ shows the corresponding web service URL for the corresponding example.

The value of the SKOS subject from DBpedia is then compared to our dictionary of properties and unit of measure. The dictionary of properties and units of measure are populated by the DBpedia query shown in Listings 11 and 12 respectively. An instance of the SSN Property class will be created if the tag can be found in the dictionary of properties. For example, a tag *Temperature* will produce an instance of the SSN *Property* and *foaf:homepage* property with <http://dbpedia.org/resource/Temperature>

¹⁷<http://sw.opencyc.org/webservices/text/tag?inputText=Temperature&disambiguate=true>

Listing 11: Query of Populating Properties Dictionary

```
select distinct ?s where {
  ?s
  <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#broader>
  <http://dbpedia.org/resource/Category:Physical_quantities>
}
```

Listing 12: Query of Populating Unit of Measure Dictionary

```
select distinct ?s where {
  ?s
  <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#broader>
  <http://dbpedia.org/resource/Category:Units_of_measure>
}
```

as its value. If the tag is an unit of measurement, then another query to DBpedia using SKOS broader property is executed to get SKOS:broader properties to that tag. The SKOS:broader properties values are then checked to the dictionary of properties and if it found there, then an instance of the corresponding property will be created. For example, the tag *Celsius* will generate an instance of *SSN Property* and *foaf:homepage* property with `http://dbpedia.org/resource/Category:Temperature` as its value.

2.3.3 Sensor Description and Output Publication

Once the RDF is generated, we use D2R Server [11] to publish instances, so that they can be browsed through HTTP based URI for either the concepts and the instances. Figure 14 depicts the publication of Pachube2RDF Sensor Output conforming to SSN Ontology.

After we have Pachube Sensor Data published in this manner, we can do some activities that were not possible before, like retrieving all the sensors measuring temperature. Listing 13 shows to get all sensors measuring temperature. Figure 15 shows the list of sensors measuring temperature.

An example of a complex query derives from the possibility of inferring geographical regions from sensors location. For instance, the distance between a sensor node and a specific location can be calculated based on geographical coordinates. This means that new type of queries can be solved, such as: "Which are the sensors that measure temperature in Ljubljana?". Such a question can be solved in Cyc by using the `distanceBetween` predicate, which can calculate the distance between two locations based on their latitude and longitude coordinates. The advantage of having access to a large knowledge base that

D2R Server
 Running at <http://denebola.dia.fi.upm.es:2020/>

[Home](#) | [Deployment](#) | [Observation](#) | [PachubeObservationValue](#) | [Platform](#) | [Property](#) | [Sensor](#) | [SensorOutput](#) | [SpaceRegion](#) | [System](#)

This is a database published with D2R Server. It can be accessed using

1. your plain old web browser
2. Semantic Web browsers
3. SPARQL clients.

1. HTML View

You can use the navigation links at the top of this page to explore the database.

2. RDF View

You can also explore this database with **Semantic Web browsers** like [Tabulator](#) or [Disco](#). To start browsing, open this entry point URL in your Semantic Web browser:

<http://denebola.dia.fi.upm.es:2020/all>

3. SPARQL Endpoint

SPARQL clients can query the database at this SPARQL endpoint:

<http://denebola.dia.fi.upm.es:2020/sparql>

The database can also be explored using [this AJAX-based SPARQL Explorer](#).

Generated by [D2R Server](#)

Figure 14: Publication of Pachube2RDF

incorporates common sense knowledge is highlighted in this example, where we already have represented the concepts of cities, also with details about their location. Then, we can assume that by "sensor located in Ljubljana" it is meant a fixed distance between city coordinates and sensor coordinates. For instance, we can consider that an area of 10 kilometers from the city coordinates is in the city region. An illustration of this query and the answer provided is represented in Figure 16.

2.4 Conclusion

in this section, we have reported our initiative of publishing and linking sensor output from the GSN and Pachube platforms. Our work enables the discovery of sensor networks in both platforms was not possible before, like getting all sensors that measure certain property (e.g. temperature) or deployed at a certain place (e.g. Ljubljana). However, there are still limitations to be tackled. The most important issue is extracting properties and features of interest from Pachube. We discovered that with our approach, we can just extract around 10% of properties, out of all tags. Furthermore, we are not yet able to extract features of interest. More work has to be done and more DBpedia properties to

Listing 13: Getting all sensors measuring temperature

```
SELECT DISTINCT * WHERE {  
  ?s a <http://purl.oclc.org/NET/ssnx/ssn#Sensor>.  
  ?s <http://purl.oclc.org/NET/ssnx/ssn#observes> ?property.  
  ?property <http://xmlns.com/foaf/spec/homepage>  
    <http://dbpedia.org/resource/Temperature>.  
}
```

be explored in order to extract more information from Pachube. However, as the tags are entered freely from users, we believe it will be difficult to develop an approach that can exploit Pachube or GSN to their fully potential use.

SPARQL:

```

PREFIX db: <http://denebola.dia.fi.upm.es:2020/resource/>
PREFIX DUL: <http://www.lob-cnr.it/ontologie/DUL.owl#>
PREFIX foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/spec/>
PREFIX ssn: <http://purl.oclc.org/NET/ssnx/ssn#>
PREFIX pachube2rdf: <http://denebola.dia.fi.upm.es/pachube2rdf#>
PREFIX rdfa: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX time: <http://www.w3.org/2006/time#>
PREFIX d2r: <http://sites.wiwiwi.de/berlin.de/suhl/bisex/d2r-server/config.rdf#>
PREFIX owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#>
PREFIX map: <file://home/epriyatna/applications/d2r-server=0.7/pachube2rdf.n3#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
PREFIX vocab: <http://denebola.dia.fi.upm.es:2020/vocab/resource/>

SELECT DISTINCT * WHERE {
  ?s a <http://purl.oclc.org/NET/ssnx/ssn#Sensor>.
  ?s <http://purl.oclc.org/NET/ssnx/ssn#observes> ?property.
  ?property <http://xmlns.com/foaf/spec/homepage> <http://dbpedia.org/resource/Temperature>.
}
LIMIT 10

```

Results:

SPARQL results:

s	property
db:Sensor/29837/0	db:Property/1
db:Sensor/12466/1	db:Property/4
db:Sensor/1846/0	db:Property/9
db:Sensor/9352/0	db:Property/15
db:Sensor/15526/0	db:Property/31
db:Sensor/21544/0	db:Property/33

Figure 15: List of sensors measuring temperature

QUERY: (What are the sensors that measure temperature in Ljubljana?)

(and
 (isa ?X Sensor)
 (hasDataStream ?X ?DS)
 (measures ?DS Temperature)
 (distanceBetween ?X CityOfLjubljanaSlovenia
 (Kilometer ?DIST))
 (lessThan ?DIST 10))

ANSWERS:

?X	?DS	?DIST
CityCenterSensor	CityCenterSensor-Data1	3.2271206217234605
IJSSensor	IJSSensor-Data1	2.4810075343716043

Figure 16: Example of a query and its answers in OpenCyc

3 Linked Stream Data

Starting in 2009, work on producing Linked Data from data emitted by sensors was initiated, pioneered by Sequeda et al. [65] and Le-Phuoc et al. [44]. Linked Stream Data is defined in [65] as the application of Linked Data principles to sensor-based data. For the sake of self-containment of this report, we will reiterate the principles of Linked Data [10], which are:

1. Use URIs to identify things.
2. Use HTTP URIs.
3. Provide useful information when the URI is dereferenced.
4. Link to other URIs.

The philosophy behind Linked Data is to provide a machine understandable representation of data and to link this data so that it becomes discoverable and allows reasoning. As a result, properly exposing and linking data is essential for the success of the Web 3.0 and, consequently for the Web of Things. According to the principles of Linked Data, each entity should have at least three corresponding dereferenceable URIs [34]:

1. URI for the real-world object itself.
2. URI for a related information resource that describes the real-world object and has an HTML representation.
3. URI for a related information resource that describes the real-world object and has an RDF/XML representation.

However, current sensor-based data streams are normally produced and emitted as *data silos*, in the sense that they are independent and isolated from each other and they are not connected to other datasets on the Web. Besides, of course, not all the previous principles are considered when publishing and querying sensor-based data in existing platforms. For instance, SensorBase [18] uses HTTP Post mechanisms to publish sensor data and provides Web Services to query it. In a similar spirit, SensorMap [57] also provides Web Services to query the sensor data. GSN [2] takes a different approach, which is using HTTP queries with parameters as the query form. Probably the most simple solution has been designed by Pachube [33] by using RESTful interfaces for both publishing and querying sensor data.

3.1 Benefits and Challenges of Linked Stream Data

Publishing the related information that describes a real world object and its associated data in HTML and RDF/XML representations is straightforward once it is available. However, in the case of embedded devices, which may have intermittent internet connectivity and may also be mobile, obtaining such information is non-trivial for meaningful descriptions (beyond MAC address, potential

IP address). For instance, looking at the sensors connected to Pachube, it can be seen that the available description resumes to what is manually provided by the publishers. However, if the future is to offer services which will require information, such as the precision of a temperature sensor located on an embedded device with a given URI, this information will need to be automatically collected for the billions of such devices connected to the Internet.

Linked Stream Data brings benefit to both the sensor data domain as well as to Linked Data domain. To the Linked Data domain, Linked Stream Data contributes a number of sensor datasets. Until the moment of writing, the growth of Linked Data is triggered and influenced mainly by the amount of data it holds [36]. To the sensor data domain, Linked Stream data bring characteristics that so far are enjoyed by Linked Data domain, such as the semantics that provide better searching, reasoning through ontologies, and integration with other data sets (especially geographic ones). The benefits of Linked Stream data also comes with the challenges like discussed in [22]. Those accompanying challenges are the abstraction level, quality of the data, integration, identification, and rapid development of applications.

3.2 Generation of Linked Stream Data from sensors

3.2.1 The Semsense Architecture

The process of publishing sensor data on the web involves several steps and poses different challenges. Starting with collecting the data from the sensing devices and resulting with public datasets containing measurements and the related metadata, various methods can be applied in the process. We propose the SemSense architecture comprising four basic components as illustrated in Figure 17: (1) the data collection component, (2) the storage component (3) the semantic enrichment component and (4) the publishing component.

Figure 17: SemSense Architecture

The data collection component contains modules which permit automatic data collection from a network of sensors. This component can be implemented using several approaches. One approach is to use a communication protocol which permits automatic meta-data collection and a server which receives the measurements and requests data about previously unknown sensors. Another approach is to define an API through which users can upload meta-data and the feed of measurements.

The storage component comprises modules for efficient storing of the data obtained from the sensors, i.e. meta-data and measurements. Depending on the amount of data and the frequency of its arrival, this component can use a simple database solution, a distributed database solution, or a combination of the two.

The semantic enrichment component includes modules that semantically enrich meta-data and measurements. This component uses vocabularies (i.e. ontologies) and mapping rules for defining the relationships between and within the data and meta-data in the storage component.

The publishing component contains modules which enable exposing the sensor information on the Web. The data publishing can be performed according to various Web standards and, accordingly, can expose more or less semantics.

- Sensesense Data Collection Component. The data collection components can be implemented using several approaches. Two that scale are based on crowdsourcing, like in the case of Pachube, and automatizing the collection from sensor networks. The latter assumes as many sensors as possible that have an "ID card" or a "technical data sheet" stored locally, which can be used to identify themselves upon request. Crowdsourcing is currently widely used for collecting large amount of data, however, to be dependable, users need to be incentivized somehow to contribute. Automatizing the collection is more dependable provided the individual sensors can be reached and questioned about themselves. This, however, implies the implementation of an appropriate identification protocol.

In this work we propose the implementation of an automatic sensor data collection module based on the Self Identification Protocol (SIDP) [54]. It was implemented for a star topology where N sensor nodes are wirelessly connected to a coordinator. The coordinator acts as a gateway for the sensor network having a wired connection to the Internet. SIDP is a simple two-message connectionless protocol. When the data collection server receives sensor measurements from a sensor node with an unknown identifier, it buffers the measurements and invokes the local instance of the SIDP_srv. SIDP_srv sends an identification request to the coordinator of the sensor network containing the address of the un-identified node and waits for the identification response.

When the instance of the SIDP_sensor in the sensor node receives the identification request, it replies to the server with an identification response which is a predefined message containing the types of sensors it has attached and the phenomenon each of these measures. The coordinator

forwards the response from SIDP_sensor to SIDP_srv which creates a new node description and saves the buffered measurements in the database. In case of repeated failures of receiving an identification message, the server drops the temporarily buffered measurements and the intent of registering the new node.

In cases where the sensor nodes themselves do not have the capability of providing positioning information (GPS coordinates), SIDP can be used by the Mobile Gateway to send geo-tagging information to the server. The sensor measurements are regularly pushed by the coordinator nodes to the server using a custom data collection protocol. However, this can be replaced by a standard data collection protocol, for instance running on top of uIPv6 of the Contiki¹⁸ operating system, if the latter is ported on the VSN platform. The described SIDP for data collection component has been implemented and tested on VSN [52] sensor nodes.

- Sensesense Storage Component. Depending on the amount of data and the frequency of its arrival, there are several approaches for implementing the storage component. Database management systems are a suitable solution for implementing this component as they can provide different abstraction levels for enhancing user interaction with the data, methods for data analysis and querying and can also handle large volumes of data [6]. Two basic approaches exist for storing sensor data. One is using distributed storage on the sensor network level (e.g. TinyDB) and the other is using centralized storage on the middle level (e.g. MySQL, Oracle, etc). The advantage of the first approach is that the data is retrieved directly from the sensor node, whereas in the second approach larger volumes of data can be handled.

Given the limited size of the sensor network¹⁹ used for the demonstration we decided that, for the implementation of the storage component, a centralized MySQL database server is sufficient for storing both the meta-data and sensor measurements. The sensor data is automatically filled in the database tables by the data collection server, while the sensor measurements are sent to the database from each node using a custom data collection protocol.

The database design is closely related to the hardware design where the sensor node features a set of sensors (devices sensitive to physical phenomena) generating measurements. The database schema is composed of four tables, as shown in Figure 18. The three upper tables, Sensor Node, Sensor and Sensor Type store the meta-data describing the physical devices and phenomena observed. The Sensor Node Table stores information about each sensor node deployed in the network, providing unique IDs, text descriptions and geographical coordinates of the locations where the sensor nodes are deployed. The Sensor Table is used to uniquely identify

¹⁸<http://www.sics.se/contiki/>

¹⁹<http://gsn.ijs.si/>

the sensing devices attached to the sensor nodes. The description of the sensing devices is provided in the Sensor Type Table, which contains information about the physical device used and the phenomena it observes. The lower table stores the sensor measurements with their timestamp, numerical value of the measurements and the corresponding sensor ID. The meta-data and data are separated in this way to avoid overhead in the database. However, each measurement can be linked back to the sensor (through Sensor ID) and to the node (through Sensor Node ID) when needed to retrieve the full context. This kind of separate data and meta-data management makes it easy to establish virtual sensor networks on higher levels of abstraction.

Figure 18: Database Schema

GPS coordinates are stored as meta-data in this implementation as all the sensor nodes used in our work are fixed at this point in time. However, once sensors are mobile, the GPS modules themselves will be considered sensors and their measurements will be saved in the Measurement Table. A sensor node can have several sensors attached to it. Currently our testbed contains sensor nodes where each node has six sensors. Multiple sensors on the same node can be of the same type and they could measure the same phenomena (e.g. temperature). Generally, the number of sensors on one node is not fixed and it can vary for every node.

- Sensesense Semantic Enrichment Component. The semantic enrichment component can be implemented using vocabularies and ontologies related to the sensor network domain. The development of semantic sensor networks in the recent years brought forth a number of ontologies describing the sensor networks domain. A detailed survey is provided in [20], where eleven sensor network ontologies are analyzed. Therefore, considering the need of standardization regarding sensor networks ontologies, an incubator group has been formed by W3C with the purpose of developing ontologies

for sensor networks, referred to as Semantic Sensor Network (SSN) ontology, and search for appropriate methods for enhancing available standards with semantic technologies. In order to provide meaning for the data published we have chosen representative concepts from related ontologies. The majority of the concepts used are from the SSN ontology which is a sensor network specific ontology. Its alignment with the DOLCE Ultra Lite upper ontology helps in describing linked data resources.

1. Semantic Vocabulary. Our experimentation work required just a subset of the SSN ontology concepts and relationships. Thus, we will provide details just on those concepts, as illustrated in Figure 19. The class System represents a sensing infrastructure and its sub-systems can be represented using the predicate hasSubSystem. The instances of the System class correspond to the sensor nodes from a network. The physical location of a sensor node is represented by the class Platform, which can have multiple systems attached.

Figure 19: Subset of concepts and relationships from the SSN ontology

The class Sensor is used to represent concrete sensing objects and the predicate observes indicates the Property monitored by a sensor (e.g. temperature, humidity). In order to represent sensor devices the class SensingDevice can be used, which inherits all the properties of the classes Sensor and Device. For representing sensor measurements we have used three classes: Observation, SensorOutput and ObservationValue. An observation represents a situation in which a value of a property is estimated by a sensor. The result of an observation is a sensor output which has a specific value.

For the geographical location of the platforms, on which the sensors are attached, we have used concepts from other ontologies that are also part of linked data cloud. For latitude and longitude coordinates we have used the Basic GeoWGS84 Vocabulary²⁰, which

²⁰<http://www.w3.org/2003/01/geo/>

provides the namespace for representing the coordinates. In addition, for geographical names we have used GeoNames database in RDF format. Links to our platforms were represented using the based_near predicate from FOAF²¹ ontology. Each platform was linked to the nearby location, based on geographical coordinates and determined using the findNearbyPlaceName web service provided by GeoNames.

2. Semantic Mapping. For the mapping between the database content and the corresponding semantic concepts we have used the D2RQ language [12]. The mapping was done respecting the SSN ontology and not the database structure, therefore some of the instances in the database were mapped to more than one concept, as it will be explained in the following.

The Sensor Node table and the Sensor table were mapped directly to the System respectively subclasses of the SensingDevice classes. However for the Platform class there is no unique identifier in the database specifically for sensor platforms. Therefore we used the geographical coordinates to identify the platforms, as it can be considered that at one exact point in space there cannot be more than one platform. The corresponding D2RQ mapping is represented in Figure 20. It can be observed that the platforms are defined as individuals of the LightPole class, which is then defined as a subclass of Platform and SpatialThing (the latter class is from the GeoWGS84 Vocabulary) classes.

```
map:Platform a d2rq:ClassMap;
d2rq:dataStorage map:database;
d2rq:uriPattern
"platforms/LightPole@@sensor_node_table.gps_latitude@@-
@@sensor_node_table.gps_longitude@@";
d2rq:class vocab:LightPole;
d2rq:classDefinitionLabel "Light Pole";
d2rq:additionalClassDefinitionProperty map: PlatformSubclass;
```

Figure 20: Platform mapping using D2RQ

From the Sensor Type Table we have extracted types of sensing devices which were mapped to subclasses of the SensingDevice class of SSN ontology (Figure 22) and subsequently used for specifying the type of individuals from Sensor table.

For the content related to sensor observations the unique ids from the database were used to identify all the individuals corresponding

²¹<http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>

```

map:DeviceType a d2rq:ClassMap;
d2rq:dataStorage map:database;
d2rq:uriPattern
"http://sensorlab.ijs.si:2020/vocab/resource/sensor/SensorType@
@sensor_type_table.st_uid@@";

map:sensor_type a d2rq:PropertyBridge;
d2rq:belongsToClassMap map:DeviceType;
d2rq:property rdf:type;
d2rq:constantValue rdfs:Class.

map:sensor_type_subclass a d2rq:PropertyBridge;
d2rq:belongsToClassMap map:DeviceType;
d2rq:property rdfs:subClassOf;
d2rq:constantValue ssn:SensingDevice.

```

Figure 21: Sensing Device subclasses identified using D2RQ

to Observation, SensorOutput and ObservationValue, using the URI patterns represented in Figure 22. The sensor measurements registered over the last day are mapped one by one, while for the past measurements average of the last hour is calculated in a separate view of the database and then mapped to RDF representation.

- Sensesense Publishing Component. Making sensor data publicly available enables the development of new and useful applications. The methods for publishing sensor data can vary from standardized web services, such as OGS's Sensor Observation Service (SOS), to application specific methods, as the ones used by Pachube or Sensorpedia²². However, such methods require prior knowledge of the infrastructures used, while Linked Sensor Data would enable better accessibility. Moreover, when supported for integration with existing knowledge it would increase also the usability of published data.

The last component of the architecture is the tool used for publishing the sensor (meta-)data, which generates RDF and HTML descriptions of the database content and makes it available over the HTTP protocol. We have used a publicly available D2R Sever as an implementation of this component, because it offers an interface to the database and does not require replicating the database content into a separate RDF

²²<http://www.sensorpedia.com/>

```
d2rq:uriPattern "sensor_measurements/SensorOutput-
@@sensor_measurement_table.measurement_id@";

d2rq:uriPattern "sensor_measurements/Observation-
@@sensor_measurement_table.measurement_id@";

d2rq:uriPattern "sensor_measurements/ObservationValue-
@@sensor_measurement_table.measurement_id@";
```

Figure 22: URI patterns for Observation, SensorOutput and ObservationValue individuals

triple-store. Moreover, the database content can be accessed by SPARQL clients and browsed using an HTML interface, being publicly available at <http://sensorlab.ijs.si:2020/>.

In order to provide semantic meaning for the sensor (meta-)data contained in the database, we have used existing ontologies for editing the mapping file used by the D2R Server. The D2R Server manages the URIs created for the RDF representation of the database content and allows data to be browsed and searched using web browsers or SPARQL endpoints.

One method to evaluate the dataset published is by the users, which can access, browse and query it. An illustrative example in Figure 23 considers a query given in SPARQL representation. The system finds all the sensors measuring temperature that are located in the Vic region of the city of Ljubljana.

```
SELECT DISTINCT ?s WHERE {
  ?sn ssn:hasSubSystem ?s.
  ?s ssn:observes
  <http://sensorlab.ijs.si:2020/vocab/resource/phenomenons/temperature>.
  ?sn ssn:onPlatform ?p.
```

Figure 23: SPARQL example query

The results can then be analyzed for more details using the web browser interface such as depicted in Figure 24.

sensor device #3	
Resource URI: http://sensorlab.ijs.si:2020/resource/sensor_devices/403AB8FC-3	
Home All SensingDevice	
Property	Value
is ssn:hasSubSystem of	< http://sensorlab.ijs.si:2020/resource/sensor-nodes/403AB8FC >
rdfs:label	sensor device #3
ssn:observes	< http://sensorlab.ijs.si:2020/vocab/resource/phenomenons/temperature >
rdf:type	< http://sensorlab.ijs.si:2020/vocab/resource/sensor/SensorType3 >

Figure 24: Description of a Sensor Device

3.2.2 Linked Stream Data in the meteorological domain

Now we will describe how we are generating Linked Stream Data in the meteorological domain, using data provided by automatic weather stations owned by the Spanish Meteorological Agency (Agencia Estatal de Meteorología, AEMET, <http://www.aemet.es/>). This domain contains several properties measured by sensors (such as temperature, humidity, wind speed, etc) by sensors. We will follow a structure that is different from the description done in the previous section, since we will focus mostly on the methodological guidelines to be followed in order to generate Linked Stream Data for such type of data. For that reason, we follow the approach proposed by Villazon-Terrazas et al [69], which identifies activities of specification (designing the URI scheme), modeling (selecting and developing if needed the ontology network according to which Linked Data will be generated), generation (production of the corresponding RDF), publication (making data available using the Linked Data technological principles) and exploitation (use in applications or linked to other datasets).

- Specification. The specification activity is focused on the design of URIs for both the sensor metadata and for the data itself. There have been several proposals in this direction, and there is not yet a common agreement on which should be the scheme to be used, as we described below:

One of these proposals was made by Sequeda and Corcho in 2009 [65]. This consisted in the creation of URIs that were very focused on the sensors that produce data, together with some extensions for temporal and spatial constraints, in a REST-like interface. Another proposal is based on observation-oriented URIs [37], which considers the OGC Observation & Measurement (O&M)[23] model in the generation of URIs, and hence it is more related to the SSN ontology that has been described already in this deliverable. The URIs pattern produced by [37] approach will have the order of base URI/sensor/feature/property. Of course, the sensor data can be accessed for specific time/spatial information, and from this point,

there is just a syntactic difference between [65] and [37]. The order of the elements is important and a wildcard for each element can be represented by dash ('-') character. The most recent paper on this area is [25], and it is the basis of the work herewith presented on the production of Linked Data from automatic weather stations. As an example of what is becoming now common practice in URI design for Linked Stream Data, the design of URIs pattern for this domain is separated into:

1. Base URI structure. The common base URI is defined as the URI of the hosting domain, in this case `http://aemet.linkeddata.es/`. Furthermore, the separation between TBox and ABox URIs is made. For TBox URIs, `ontology/` is added together with the local name of the resource. For ABox URIs `resource/` is added.
 2. TBox URIs. The design of TBox URIs is furthermore refined in this step. For class type element, the local name is the name of the class written with camel case style started with upper case letter, while for property type element is writing with camel class style as well, but started with lower case letter.
 3. ABox URIs. One important aspect when designing URIs is that every resource should be assigned unique URI, so that it wont be misinterpreted with another resources. While this is a relatively easy task in designing URIs for TBox, this task becomes very hard for ABox URIs. The paper presents the use of Patterned URIs²³ combined with some ad hoc approach for representing temporal aspect.
- Modeling. For the modelling phase, general Linked Data production guidelines suggest looking for available ontologies that deal with the concepts and properties that are related to the data being exposed. In the case of Linked Sensor Data, it is clear that one of those ontologies is the W3C SSN Ontology that has been already described. Besides this ontology, extensions can be made in order to represent the specific features of interest that are addressed (e.g., in the case of meteorological information, mainly geographical features, and in Spain), and the properties that are observed (e.g., amount of rain, wind speed, etc.).

The ontology network used in this case can be seen in figure 25.

- Generation. After the specification and the modeling tasks have been done, the focus is turned to the generation task. For that purpose, we will separate this task into 3 separate subtasks, according to Linked Data main elements, which are schema, instances, and links.
 - Schema generation. While the schema generation for Linked Data has been proposed by [68] and [50], not much work has been devoted in the domain of Linked Stream Data. One work that we are aware

²³<http://patterns.dataincubator.org/book/patterned-uris.html>

Figure 25: AEMET ontology network conceptual model

of is the adaptation of the work [68] which is done in [66]. The authors proposed the generation of wrapping ontologies from the sensor metadata and sensor data. In order to do that, the authors proposed 3 steps. First step is the generation of ontology from the base relations and base stream. It then continued in the second step by generating ontology from the derived relation and stream. The final step is to combine the ontologies produced in the first and second step.

- Instances generation. The instances generation is mostly done by transforming stream data into instances of the selected ontologies. However, as stream data has unique characteristics, then it needs special representation. There are two major approaches for representing stream data, which are stRDF [41] and temporal RDF [32]. Temporal RDF just encodes temporal aspect into RDF instances while stRDF takes into account spatial aspect as well as temporal aspect. It is worth noting that the instance generation task seems to be the only active research compared to the schema or link generation.
- Links generation. Together with schema generation, links generation does not experience so much work, even though it can be thought that the linking part is a very important aspect in Linked Stream

Data. The links can be generated, either by observing the sensor metadata, or sensor data itself. To the best of our knowledge, no significant work has been done on generating links from the sensor data itself. A recent work has been done for generating links from the sensor metadata in [40]. In that work, the sensor metadata is first converted into RDF documents, then keywords are extracted. User are then presented with the keywords and have the ability to define `owl:sameAs` relations. Furthermore, their system can give users some recommendations by using the authors previous work on similarity-based information retrieval.

- **Publication.** After the instances have been generated, the next step is to publish them. One common way to publish the result into Linked Open Data is by storing the result in triple stores. Some examples of triples stores are Virtuoso Universal Server, 4Store, and many others. The users can then be presented with Linked Data explorer features such as Pubby.
- **Exploitation.** Sometimes exploring the data from the publication task result is not enough for the users. Instead of exploring data, users might have some specific queries in their mind. For this reason, Linked Stream Data has to have the ability allow querying. In a similar consideration when designing representation of Linked Sensor Data instances, spatial and temporal aspect should be taken into account also in the query. To query instances represented in temporal RDF [32], SPARQL queries have to be equipped with built-in functions related to time and interval. Such queries do not add the complexity in the query answering procedure. For the other representation, stRDF, the query language used is stSPARQL [41], however, the complexity of this query language is not studied there. [16] presents an RDF stream as sequence of pairs (T_i, τ_i) where T_i is an RDF triple and τ_i is a timestamp which comes from a monotonically non-decreasing sequence. RDF Stream is queried through a language called *SPARQL_{Stream}*, which is an extension to SPARQL for streaming RDF data, RDF Stream. The result of executing the query, be it a CONSTRUCT or SELECT form, is an XML document, which will be available at a URI provided by the system. In order to get result from the newest stream, users have to access again the provided URI. Such mechanism is call pull-based. We have not encountered any push-based Linked Stream Data so far. Some candidates for push-based Linked Stream Data might include SOAP, WS Subscription, RSS-based result, or pubpubsubsub [58].

3.3 Conclusion

In this section we have analysed two alternatives for the production of Linked Sensor Data, coming from real-world sensing objects. In both cases, these data are related to the environmental domain. We have also reflected over the methodological guidelines that are needed, and the technological infrastructure that is required, in order to produce and consume such data. There is still

work to do in the standardisation of approaches for the generation of URIs, or in the development of robust technological infrastructure that can give support to Linked Sensor Data, and hence the future work should be directed towards that area.

4 Characterisation mechanisms for Text Data Streams

In this section we describe two approaches for the characterisation of textual data streams, which have many differences with respect to the work that we did for sensor-based data sources. In fact, in this case we focus mostly on the characterisation of the data itself, instead of only the framework or infrastructure generating such data.

We will start describing an approach for the characterisation of social media texts which consists of POS tagging, topic recognition, topic categorization, language filtering and the implementation of the approach. Next we will describe an algorithm for only hierarchical clustering for organizing a stream of documents in the presence of topic drift.

4.1 Characterisation of social media texts by means of topic recognition

We now present our work for characterisation mechanisms in text published in social media, by applying topic recognition techniques that exploit DBpedia. By social media contents, we mean content generated by users, such as blogs, tweets, social network, and review sites. We consider such contents as streams of text. Our approach identifies topics in the content and links those topics to DBpedia resources, as DBpedia is one of the most important elements in Linked Open Data cloud, which furthermore links to important ontologies such as OpenCyc, YAGO, and WordNet. The approach consists of the following pipeline processes: part-of-speech tagging, topic recognition, topic categorization, and language filtering. Each of the process will be explained in more detail.

4.1.1 Part-of-speech Tagging

This process takes the text of p as an input and returns a set of keywords K_p that appear in such text. In this process, we first annotate the words in p with their lexical category, only whose category is one of the following: *common noun*, *proper noun*, *acronym*, *foreign word*, and *unit of measure*. Those words will be annotated also with their lemmas. Lemma that is not in θ , which is a set of stop words, will be returned from this process as a keyword. Listing 14 defines the process of POS tagging.

4.1.2 Topic Recognition

This process receives K_p and returns the set of topics T_p , as semantic entities derived from K_p . In this process, each of the keywords as the result from the previous result, will be linked to a DBpedia resource. For this purpose, each of the keyword has to be preprocessed so we can get the *normalized* version of the keyword. The normalized version of the keyword can be retrieved utilizing Wikipedia redirection page if the keyword is considered an alternative version of

the Wikipedia article title. In case the spelling of the keyword is wrong, Yahoo! spelling and suggestion service is used to correct the misspelled keyword. In the case the normalized keyword returns an Wikipedia article, then the DBpedia resource of the corresponding article is added to the set of topics, which is the result of this process. When the normalized keyword returns multiple articles, we use Sem4Tags [30] to give us the intended article of the keyword. In order to carry out this task, the following tasks are executed by Sem4Tags:

1. Active Contexts Selection. In this task, Sem4Tags calculate the active contexts of the keywords. A context is defined as the set of keyword for the analysed text. Active context is the subset of the whole context. The members of the active context are the most related words for the analysed text, usually 4 most related words, and they are calculated using the technique described in [31].
2. Disambiguation Process. The set of articles returned by the ambiguous keyword is used as candidate senses. The disambiguation process selects the most appropriate sense for the keyword. Following Lesk's idea [47] we can measure how similar is the definition of each sense with respect to the context of the ambiguous word, and then select the most similar sense. To do so we use a model where each of the candidate senses (i.e., Wikipedia articles) as well as the keyword and its context are represented as a vector. First we create the *Vocabulary* set as the union of the top N frequent terms in each of the candidate senses. Next, for each sense we create a vector in $\mathbb{R}^{|Vocabulary|}$ where each position corresponds to an element in an ordered version of the *Vocabulary* set. The value w_i associated with the i -th position in the vector is calculated using TF-IDF²⁴ [5] for the corresponding i -th term in the ordered set. Note that IDF is calculated only in the set of candidate senses.

Listing 15 illustrates the Topic Recognition process.

²⁴TF-IDF stands for Term Frequency and Inverse Document Frequency

Listing 14: Definition of the POS Tagging process

```

def GetKeywords( $W_p$ ) :
     $K_p \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
    for each  $w_i$  in  $W_p$  :
        if  $lexcat(w_i) \in L$  and  $lemma(w_i) \notin \theta$  :
             $K_p \leftarrow K_p \cup \{lemma(w_i)\}$ 
    return  $K_p$ 
```

Listing 15: Definition of the Topic Recognition process

```

def GetSemanticTopics( $K_p$ ) :
   $T_p \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
  for each  $k_i$  in  $K_p$  :
     $k_i \leftarrow PreProcessing(k_i)$ 
     $AC \leftarrow GetActiveContext(k_i, K_p)$ 
    if Ambiguous( $k_i$ ) :
       $Senses \leftarrow GetDisambiguationLinks(k_i)$ 
       $sense_j \leftarrow Disambiguate(k_i, AC, Senses)$ 
       $T_p \leftarrow T_p \cup GetDBpediaResource(sense_j)$ 
    else :
       $T_p \leftarrow T_p \cup GetDBpediaResource(k_i)$ 
  return  $T_p$ 

```

Listing 16: Definition of the Topic Categorization process

```

def CategorizeTopics( $T_p$ ) :
   $C_p \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
  for each  $t_i$  in  $T_p$  :
     $C_p \leftarrow C_p \cup Categories(t_i)$ 
  return  $C_p$ 

```

4.1.3 Topic Categorization

This process receives the set of topics T_p from the previous tasks and returns the set of categories C_p to which the topics in T_p belong. The member c of the set of categories C_p is calculated using the value *dcterms:subject* from the topic t in T_p . Listing 16 illustrates the Topic Categorization process.

4.1.4 Language Filtering

This process receives T_p and C_p and returns the set of topics T_p^l and the set of categories C_p^l than have been defined for a language l . In order to do that, the label of each topic will be retrieved via the statement :

```
<t> rdfs : label <e>
```

Then, only the topics whose the language of the label matches l will be passed as the result. Listing 17 illustrates this process.

4.1.5 Implementation

We have implemented the method with the workflow shown in figure 26. The integration layer has been implemented with Apache Camel. We have defined

Listing 17: Definition of the Language Filtering process

```

def FilterLanguage( $T_p, C_p, l$ ) :
   $T_p^l \Leftarrow C_p^l \Leftarrow \emptyset$ 
  for each  $t_i$  in  $T_p$  :
    if  $\exists b_j \in Labels(t_i) | lang(b_j) = l$  :
       $T_p^l \Leftarrow T_p^l \cup \{t_i\}$ 
  for each  $c_i$  in  $C_p$  :
    if  $\exists b_k \in Labels(c_i) | lang(b_k) = l$  :
       $C_p^l \Leftarrow C_p^l \cup \{c_i\}$ 
  return ( $T_p^l, C_p^l$ )

```

an annotation pipeline with Gate [24] for handling the overall NLP process, while the component in charge of performing the POS tagging is TreeTagger [64]. We have used the RESTful interface of the Sem4Tags service ²⁵ for identifying topics. Finally, our implementation obtains the categories and filters the language of a given corpus in the same step by performing SPARQL [61] [19] queries to the DBpedia SPARQL endpoint.

4.1.6 Evaluation

We have evaluated our method with a corpora of 10,000 posts. Such corpora has been gathered by crawling posts related with the telecommunications domain from the following kinds of media channels:

- Web logs. We have extracted the texts of the posts from the feeds of blog publishing platforms such as Wordpress and Blogger.
- Forums. We have scraped the text of the comments published in web forums constructed with vBulletin and phpBB technologies.
- Microblogs (e.g., Twitter and Tumbler). We have extracted the short messages published in such channels by querying their APIs.
- Social networks (e.g., Facebook, MySpace, LinkedIn and Xing). We have extracted the messages published in such channels by querying their APIs.
- Review sites (e.g., Ciao and Dooyoo). We have scraped the text of the comments published in such channels.
- Audiovisual content publishing sites (e.g., YouTube and Flickr). We have extracted the textual comments associated to the audiovisual content.
- News publishing sites. We have extracted the articles from the feeds published in such channels.

²⁵<http://grafias.dia.fi.upm.es/Sem4Tags/webService.htm>

Figure 26: Implemented workflow

- Other sites not classified in the categories above (e.g., Content Management Systems) that publish their content as feeds, or that have a known HTML structure from which a scrapping technique can be applied.

Figure 27 shows the coverage of the method. The POS tagging process gives a nearly 100% coverage for all types of medias. The Topic Recognition and Topic Categorization tasks were evaluated with three variants. The first is to evaluate the most appropriate sense without using any contexts, so the most appropriate sense is selected from the default link of Wikipedia articles. The second variant is using all the keywords as the context and the third variant is using active context selection. We discover that the second and last variants work better than the first variant in both tasks.

Figure 28 shows the precision of the method. As the previous evaluation, this is also evaluated with three variants. We discovered that for the Topic Recognition, the first variant gives a better result than the variants using context or active context. For the Topic Categorization task, the variant using active context selection gives a better result than the first variant, but the first variant is still better when compared to the second variant.

	Blogs	Forums	Microblogs	Soc. N.	Others	Reviews	Audiovisual	News	All
POS Tagged	99.63%	96.64%	99.01%	98.14%	98.77%	98.53%	97.20%	99.52%	98.38%
<i>Topic Recognition</i>									
Without context	96.7%	87.68%	94.22%	93.54%	92.71%	88.81%	90.29%	96.67%	92.35%
With context	96.64%	93.07%	95.54%	94.99%	95.13%	92.67%	97.41%	98.54%	95.02%
Active context	99.24%	89.71%	94.43%	96.4%	94.75%	93.81%	92.23%	97.4%	94.72%
<i>Topic Recognition (after language filtering)</i>									
Without context	91.21%	79.04%	87.54%	82.64%	86.93%	70.15%	82.52%	90.71%	82.74%
With context	88.43%	80.84%	86.31%	85.24%	88.72%	76.19%	89.66%	92.46%	84.85%
Active context	89.69%	80.51%	86.51%	86.78%	89.78%	75.59%	80.58%	90.54%	84.73%
<i>Topic Categorization (after language filtering)</i>									
Without context	87.18%	77.39%	84.19%	87.48%	86.98%	82.65%	83.50%	93.33%	85.26%
With context	88.06%	80.29%	87.50%	87.74%	89.49%	82.60%	84.48%	95.62%	86.74%
Active context	91.98%	81.25%	84.46%	89.19%	87.85%	86.89%	81.55%	91.96%	87.22%

Figure 27: Coverage of the method

	Blogs	Forums	Microblogs	Soc. N.	Others	Reviews	Audiovisual	News	All
<i>Topic Identification</i>									
Without context	67.48%	66.67%	59.72%	72.32%	59.19%	79.17%	84.44%	71.95%	68.42%
With context	75.61%	59.35%	54.88%	65.71%	53.52%	83.87%	77.78%	64.37%	63.11%
Active context	67.71%	64.45%	65.58%	70.1%	49.15%	88.89%	79.07%	71.93%	66.59%
<i>Topic Categorization</i>									
Without context	56.07%	52.06%	39.48%	58.29%	50.99%	71.43%	73.56%	52.65%	53.87%
With context	58.21%	48.8%	43.39%	52.9%	46.22%	54%	73.85%	47.12%	50.27%
Active context	59.44%	57.41%	41.11%	53.17%	50.14%	67.65%	62.12%	59.47%	54.01%

Figure 28: Precision of the method

4.2 Efficient Clustering of Document Streams

The lowering of entry costs for publishing information online in recent years has provided researchers with an unprecedented amount of textual data available.

From online news articles, which are published at a rate of approximately one per second, through tens of blog posts per second, to finally thousands of short notifications posted through services such as Twitter, there is a large amount of redundancy present in the data, yet trying to follow many such sources can quickly result in information overload.

The metadata provided with such postings is at best inconsistent in the case of tags attached to blog posts, where the author is free to pick any set of labels based on what they mean to her, to not available at all in the case of badly designed news sites, leading some researchers to point out that it can, especially in the case of nonprofessional authors, be treated just as additional content, not as labels ([9]).

As the postings are created and published sequentially in time, it is natural

to represent them not merely as a set but as a time-ordered sequence, or a stream, of documents. Since no obvious time delineation exists — when taking into account a large portion of the world even the daily rhythm disappears — and the process of creation never stops, the source of such a stream can be regarded as infinite for all practical concerns.

Since subject matter of discussion and commenting continuously arises, evolves and fades away, we can not model such a source as a static one but need to constantly adapt the learned models.

The problem then is how to organize a never-ending sequence of documents in the presence of topic drift efficiently enough to be able to handle from tens to thousands of them each second and continuously provide a real-time model of the changing world.

The contribution of the work presented here is an online hierarchical clustering algorithm which tries to maintain such a model and its evaluation on two datasets.

4.2.1 Proposed algorithm

Our proposed algorithm is designed to efficiently maintain a real-time clustering of a portion of a dataset in the presence of topic drift, without using any assumptions about the distributions of component of vectors representing the datapoints.

The input to the algorithm is a sequence of datapoints, which are elements of a \mathbb{R}^n vector space, labeled with a timestamp or a sequence number. This number is only used to decide when the datapoint falls out of the specified window and should be forgotten.

The model is represented by a tree structure with two types of nodes — clusters and datapoints (Fig. 29).

Figure 29: A demonstration of the proposed algorithm results after t steps built on a stream of documents from three categories. Clusters are represented with circles while other shapes represent datapoints belonging to different categories. The model was constrained to 30 datapoints and the distribution of the input changed during the run.

Clusters are always internal nodes of the tree and can have a mixture of clusters and datapoints as children — the datapoints need not be located only in the bottom-most clusters, unlike with BIRCH. Each cluster also contains a summary vector, which is always a component-wise sum of all the datapoints contained within that cluster — direct descendants and descendants of all of its subclusters. When the summary is represented as a sparse vector, which it would usually be in the case of text clustering, the summary vector is pruned to a much smaller dimension than a direct sum of the datapoints would have by removing the components with smallest values — otherwise the cost of comparing summaries increases with the number of datapoints in the tree.

- Events in the model. There are two events defined for the model: arrival and expiration of a datapoint. Handling them only differs in the first step of the model update.

When a datapoint needs to be inserted into the tree, the best matching node is found using a beam search from the tree root (cluster representing the entire dataset) as a starting point. The beam width is a configurable parameter and its effects are shown in the result section. Comparing a datapoint to a cluster means comparing it to its centroid, which is simply calculated by dividing the summary vector by the number of documents in the cluster, and cosine distance is used for the comparison the two.

Upon finding the best matching cluster node, which can be any node in the tree — including the root — the datapoint is inserted among its children while the cluster is marked for structure update — a local adaptation of the tree described in the next section.

The datapoint is also added to a FIFO queue or a linked list of all nodes currently in the tree, so it is possible to find the oldest datapoint.

If a datapoint needs to be removed from a tree — for example if the model reaches a predefined size or if the age of some datapoints is higher than desired — it is simply removed from its parent, and this parent is marked for structure update.

- Structure adaptation. The structure update is a local modification of the tree to better reflect the situation after addition or removal of a node. It consists of repeating a single type of reordering on all nodes on the path from the marked one to the root.

It can be performed either after every event, or multiple consecutive updates can be merged into one update sequence. Also, if the model is waiting for a new event with CPU cycles to spare, a (possibly random) node can be selected as the starting point for an update even though no change actually happened, with the hope of local improvements.

In general, to arrive at a better hierarchical clustering after some datapoints have been added or removed from the tree, a sequence of following transformations can be performed:

- merging of two clusters
- splitting a cluster into two
- lifting a cluster
- sinking a cluster

where lifting and sinking refer to moving an entire cluster up towards the root or down into a sibling in the hierarchy respectively.

Deciding when any of these operations should be performed is not a simple task without the supervision of a human operator, as the decisions depend on why the user really needs a hierarchy.

If it is possible to estimate the probability that a datapoint belongs to a cluster or that a pair of clusters is significantly more similar than another pair, a case can be made for a maximum description length approach. CluStream similarly estimates how a datapoint is similar to a cluster by calculating the standard deviation for each dimension of a cluster using the cluster summary, then comparing that to the value of the respective datapoints component.

Unfortunately, it is so far impossible to get a useful estimate of this probability based on its bag of words representation — our preliminary tests have shown the calculated probabilities to be useless for a CluStream-style approach, even though some attempts (e.g. [62]) have been made to calculate such probabilities.

An additional constraint the algorithm needs to be careful about is the branching of the tree — should the tree become strongly imbalanced, operations depending on its depth would not be $O(\log n)$ (for n being the number of datapoints in the model) on average anymore.

Instead of all the listed transformations, the local modification of a nodes neighborhood summarized in the Algorithm 1 is proposed.

All possible splits and merges (to a sibling) of a node P having a parent G are evaluated in a single step by discarding P and all of its siblings while collecting children of these nodes in a set S . Those siblings of P that are datapoints are also added to S and unlinked from G .

k -means is then used to split S into a new set of clusters which are created instead of now discarded children of G . If any of these new clusters have only a single child, this child replaces its parent among G 's children.

Treating G 's datapoint children as its grandchildren provides an implicit sinking step, while the absorption of small children in the last step serves as the inverse. While the sinking and lifting can only move single datapoints instead of clusters, it is still possible to perform an arbitrary transformation of the entire tree by repeating the outlined procedure with a careful selection of the number of clusters and the clustering step. Since it is

Algorithm 1 Local structure update for the neighborhood of the node P

Input: P the node whose children have been modified and G its parent

- 1 Collect all G 's grandchildren (which include P 's children) and G 's children that are not clusters into a set S .
This set can contain actual datapoints, clusters if any of the grandchildren were clusters or a mixture of those.
 - 2 Discard all *cluster* children of G .
 - 3 Cluster the set S using any of the known clustering algorithms, such as k -means .
 - 4 Insert newly created clusters as children of G .
 - 5 If any of these clusters contains only a single child, lift the child into G and remove the now empty cluster.
 - 6 Mark G for structure update
-

unlikely that major changes should occur due to just a couple of datapoints, this is not viewed as a severe limitation, especially in the light of experimental results.

This procedure still has one parameter left — the number of clusters to be created in the clustering step. After discarding the idea of choosing cluster sizes and/or their desired compactness relative to their siblings in the tree (which produced extraordinarily degenerate trees), a simple upper limit on the branching factor proved to give satisfactory results.

Testing this approach showed it to be beneficial (from the models stability standpoint) to relax the constraint when the branching factor was high (16 in our case) and allow a higher number of children than the specified limit if the previous number was also significantly higher — that prevents the situations when the branching factor of a node suddenly changes by a high ratio. However, even allowing such high branching factors did not prove to have a positive impact on the quality of the model in the first place.

Forcing the number of children of G to a specified limit in the above procedure produces degenerate trees with a large fan-out at the bottommost level. The actual condition for deciding the number of clusters in the clustering step is therefore not the number of cluster produced, but the upper limit on their size. This may produce more clusters than the desired branching factor, but those will then be properly redistributed in the recursive update of the G 's parent which is described in the next paragraph. If during the update of the root node the number of new clusters exceeds the branching limit, a new node is created as root with the former root node as its only child and the same procedure repeated on it.

Because the children of G changed during this procedure, the algorithm recursively performs the same operation on the entire path towards the

root of the tree, starting with G .

Elements of the set S can be either datapoints or clusters. In order to cluster all of them using a k -means algorithm, clusters are regarded as ordinary datapoints, with their centroids (calculated from the summary vector) serving as the representation. Since the cluster summary of a node high in the hierarchy contains the sum of all of the datapoints in the subtree it can contain a large number of nonzero components — the number rises approximately with $O(\sqrt{n})$ where n is the number of documents in the subtree ([43]). In order to constrain the algorithms asymptotic run time behavior to $O(\log n)$ the summary vectors need to be pruned to a constant length by discarding the smallest components.

For the experiments described here, the clustering step was implemented by a bisecting k -means algorithm. Based on [42], whose authors have shown that k -means converges much faster when performing incremental reassignments instead of interleaving the calculation of centroids and assignments in discrete steps, we implemented the bisecting step as shown in the Algorithm 2. An added benefit when implementing this step using bisecting clustering is the ability to stop the procedure whenever the resulting clusters are small enough (which is exactly the condition described earlier) instead of performing several complete k -means runs with a different number of clusters. It is important not to confuse the clusters that are produced during the bisecting k -means run with the result of this run, which is a flat clustering.

Algorithm 2 Bisecting k -means step

Input: Set B to be split into two clusters

1. Repeat 4 times:
 - 1.1. Try 6 pairs of randomly selected vectors from B and pick the two least similar as the initial centroids.
 - 1.2. Perform 3 passes over the set of datapoints, (re)assigning each datapoint to the closest centroid and updating the centroid immediately.
 - 1.3. Calculate the cluster compactness as the similarity of each document to each other (which can be calculated by squaring the centroid vector).
2. Pick the clustering with the best compactness.

Note: the constants were selected to provide a satisfactory clustering of datasets in these experiments.

The partition to be bisected next is picked from a priority queue sorted first by size of clusters (thus making certain that no oversized clusters will remain if the procedure is stopped before every cluster is of size one) and then by their compactness, splitting less partitions clusters first.

The model built by the algorithm is not meant for direct use by people

due to its limited branching factor; a post-processing step merging some of the branches can be performed to overcome this limitation.

4.2.2 Experiments

- Datasets. All of the experiments with the described algorithm were performed on two datasets.

The first dataset is the text mining standard corpus RCV1 [48] (Reuters Corpus Volume 1). It contains approximately 810.000 articles spanning a year of Reuters news. Each document is manually categorized in a shallow hierarchy of about 100 categories.

The second dataset is a set of 110.000 news articles published online on 7682 different sites during the first two weeks of January 2009. In order to obtain category labels, we followed Google News and extracted its story ID for the matching URLs. The categories are much smaller than those in RCV1: there are approximately 50 news items per category assigned to 5000 categories, with each item belonging to 2.2 categories on average. About 90% of the stories span less than a day. Since these categories are not human generated, this is not as good a golden standard as RCV1, but it represents our intended target datasets better. We call this dataset ‘online news’ in the experiments.

All of the news articles from both datasets were processed in the same manner. Words containing non-alphabetic characters and the words from the English-571 stopword list ([15]) were removed, then each remaining word was normalized using Porter stemmer [60]. The processed documents were represented as term-frequency (TF) sparse vectors and stored in the database.

All of the subsequent experiments were performed using normalized TF vectors instead of weighted TFIDF versions, except for the experiment where the ad-hoc weighting was tried out. Except where otherwise noted, documents from the beginning of the dataset were used, always in time ascending order.

Also, if not otherwise stated, the search beam width was set to 10 and the branching limit to 3.

- Evaluation measure. The authors of [67] define a generalization of the F_1 measure so that it can be used for external clustering evaluation.

Let T be the set of topics or categories in a corpus. Then for a topic $t \in T$ and a node P in the tree representing the hierarchical clustering,

$$F_1(t, P) = \frac{2 * \text{precision}(t, P) \cdot \text{recall}(t, P)}{\text{precision}(t, P) + \text{recall}(t, P)} \quad (1)$$

where $\text{precision}(t, P)$ is the precision for category t measured only on the subtree rooted in P : the number of documents belonging to the category

t in the entire subtree of P divided by the total number of documents in that subtree, and recall the same number of documents belonging to t in the subtree of P , divided with the number of documents belonging to t in the entire model.

The value $F_1(t)$ for some category t is defined as $\max_P F_1(t, P)$ over all nodes P in the tree, and the overall F_1 for the model as

$$F_1 = \frac{\sum_{t \in T} (|T| \cdot \max_P F_1(t, P))}{\sum_T |T|} \quad (2)$$

The interpretation of this is that we pick one node in the hierarchy as the representative for one category and measure F_1 for that category on the selected node only. The result is the weighted average over all categories.

This measure is not the best fit for the proposed algorithm as it consistently underestimates the intuitive quality of a clustering because of the way branching of the tree is selected, which can prevent two trees from merging into one cluster without forcing this cluster to also receive one or more subtrees containing documents from a different category (except in the case of branching factor being 2). In that case, either one of the subtrees will be selected and the recall will suffer, or the entire tree will be selected as the representative, in which case precision will fall, even though all of the subtrees could actually be perfectly clustered.

Nonetheless, we decided to use this measure instead of creating yet another one.

- Comparison reference. Since most of the algorithms for stream clustering work on domains with a small number of attributes, we compare our results to two simple baseline methods. The first one is a bisecting hierarchical k -means algorithm run on the same data window as is maintained by the proposed algorithm, giving the approximate upper bound on the results. Note that because the branching factor of the tree created by bisection is always two, the comparison is not precise, only an estimate. The second reference algorithm is the same as the proposed one, but modified so that datapoints are inserted into random clusters in the tree, and that structural updates create random partitions instead of actually performing the clustering, creating a sort of a random clustering, providing the lower bound. The branching factor of these trees was kept as close to the branching limit selected for the algorithm under test as possible.

4.2.3 Results

- Quality of the clustering. In order to determine if the algorithm works properly, we first tested it with an infinite window length, partially avoiding the problems of concept drift. Figure 30 shows F_1 measure of the proposed algorithm compared with the reference algorithms on both datasets,

when datapoints were only added to the model. The fact that our proposed algorithm performs even better than k -means could probably be attributed to a different branching factor — the k -means algorithm shares the implementation with the clustering step in the proposed algorithm which excludes simple errors that could invalidate its results.

- Concept drift. As we expect the model to quickly adapt to changing input distribution, we generated a special dataset to verify this. The dataset is a filtered version of RCV1 corpus: it consists of the first 10.000 documents from RCV1 that belong to the category CCAT, then 5.000 documents (starting with document ID 267192) sampled with equal probability from either CCAT or GCAT categories, and then another 10.000 documents from GCAT category.

The figure 31 shows the performance of the model built on this and the ‘online news’ datasets with different window sizes. The effect of the distribution change can be clearly seen on lowering of F_1 for the randomly built tree, while no such effect is observed on the static k -means and our proposed algorithm. The actual increase of the F_1 measure in the second half of the graph can be attributed to a somewhat different structure of the prevailing category in the corpus.

- Efficiency. Another very important consideration for this algorithm is its asymptotic efficiency, as it is expected to perform well even when millions of datapoints are present in the model. Figure 32 shows the cumulative time required to load datapoints in a model with an infinite window.

Given that the underlying data structure is a tree, we would expect an average $O(\log n)$ time required to insert a single datapoint if the tree is balanced, or $O(n \log(n - 1))$ to insert n datapoints. Fitting an $a \cdot n \log n$ curve to the graphs on figure 32 gives a good match, with RCV1 load slightly below the logarithmic time complexity and the *online news* corpus load slightly above.

- Idle time model improvements. Since it is possible to modify the clustering while waiting for the next datapoint from the input, we tried to simulate such circumstances by loading 5000 datapoints in a model with an infinite window, so no datapoints were discarded yet, and then performed 5000 attempts at improving the model by picking a random node in the tree and modifying the entire path from that node to the root of the tree as described in chapter 3. As can be seen on the figure 33, only small improvements can be gained in exchange for a large computational cost.
- Term weighting. Usually, the term frequencies of datapoints are weighted to decrease the importance of common words, but in the stream clustering setting, we can not precisely estimate how common a word is — one possible approximation is to use the recent history as the statistics.

(a) RCV1

(b) Online news

Figure 30: A comparison of the proposed algorithm to static k -means and a baseline.

Figure 31: Adaptation to change

Figure 32: Time needed to process n documents

We tried two simple approximations to estimating the document frequency of words which was then used to calculate the log inverse document frequency used in TFIDF weighting.

A set of word counters was maintained and whenever a document was added to the model, word counters for all the words in the document were incremented by the number of times the word occurred in the document. In one experiment, these counters were decreased by the same amount when the document was removed from the tree due to falling out of the window, and in the other the counters never decreased.

Figure 34 shows the impact of term weighting on clustering results. There is a small improvement of both methods over the baseline where only TF vectors were used, the difference between these two methods is however much less obvious.

- Model parameter tuning. The model as presented in the chapter 3 has two parameters that can be tuned: the width of the beam for the beam search algorithm and the upper branching limit for the tree.

Figures 35 and 36 show how varying these two parameters influences the quality of the model. It is apparent that high branching factors worsen the quality of the model as well as significantly increase the time needed to add a datapoint — the number of grandchildren in the clustering step 3 of Algorithm 1 increases with the square of the branching factor on average.

(a) RCV1

(b) Online news

Figure 33: Effects of idle-time restructuring of the model

(a) RCV1

(b) Online news

Figure 34: Effect of different weighting schemes

Avoiding a simple recursive search and using a beam search instead brings a significant improvement in the case of online news corpus as it helps to steer clear of the local maxima in similarity when searching for the best matching node.

4.3 Conclusion

In this section we have presented two approaches for characterising data in the form of textual streams, such as those from Twitter feeds. The first one was focused on the detection of topics dealt with in these text streams by means of assigning them Dbpedia terms, based on a mixture of information retrieval and NLP techniques, as described in the corresponding section. The results of the evaluation show that it is possible to get good quality results in this area, even if there are normally many difficulties in understanding text streams in this particular framework, given its characteristics. The another work has focused on the characterisation of documents (of any type) by clustering.

(a) RCV1

(b) Online news

Figure 35: Effect of different search beam widths

(a) RCV1

(b) Online news

Figure 36: Effect of tree branching factor limit

5 Conclusion

In this report, we discussed in detail the concept of Linked Stream Data, as well as how it is different from the traditional data. We also report the guidelines activity to generate and publish traditional data to Linked Stream Data.

We reported the systems that have been implemented to analyze data from sensor platforms such as GSN and Pachube, and how to annotate semantics to its output. It is relevant to note that all the efforts we have presented here are focused on the description of the data sources, and that access to data is always done in a poll-based. We also reported our work that implements system that analyze those output coming as text stream, such as Twitter.

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